

STANDARDIZATION OF MEDICAL PLANT RAW MATERIALS

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Standardization is a set of laws that serve the interests of all stakeholders in order to regulate the activities of an industry, and the application of these laws with their participation. Standardization based on the development of science and technology and best practices is a great service in the management of the national economy with the systematic implementation of mandatory norms, requirements and rules to state enterprises, institutions, organizations and agencies aimed at accelerating technical progress, increasing social labor productivity and improving product quality. does. These mandatory requirements, norms and rules are given in the relevant normative and technical documents. Normative and technical documents on standardization of medicinal plants provide a set of norms, requirements and rules that must be implemented in certain areas, developed in a certain order and approved by the competent authority.

The State Standardization System, which covers all sectors of the economy, was established in 1925 in the former Soviet Union. Currently, the system includes the following agencies:

1. all standardization organizations and their divisions;
 2. Departments of standardization in the national economy;
 3. Departments of standardization in the republic
- State Organization for Standardization and Metrology -
The State Committee for Standards (Gosstandart) was introduced.

The main tasks of Gosstandart:

1. Determining the main directions of development of standardization, development of scientific-methodical and technical-economic bases, unification of intersectoral industrial products and metrology;
2. Improving the system of standardization and metrology;

3. Standardization of product quality indicators (production, acceptance and analysis);

4. Introduce standards into production, adhere to them

Execution of state control over

In all regions, standardization activities are supervised by the State Planning Commission (Gosplan) and the Republican Department of Gosstandart.

In the Ministry of Health, the work on standardization is coordinated by the Scientific and Technical Department. The Pharmacopoeia Committee of the Ministry of Health is responsible for the preparation and revision of normative and technical documents for medicinal products and medicinal plant products. Category of standards. Standards are divided into the following categories and types, depending on the scope, content and level of approval:

1.State standards - GOST

Plant products that are produced in large quantities and used in all sectors of the economy are developed and approved (entered into force, amended or repealed) by a decision of the State Standard. The mark corresponding to the approved GOST is given. This symbol consists of the GOST index, the number of lists and the year of approval of GOST. For example, GOST 13.309.79. This symbol contains 13 GOST indexes, 309 - the number of standard lists of these raw materials, and 79 - the year of approval of GOST. Compliance with the requirements of state standards is mandatory for all agencies, enterprises and institutions throughout the country.

2. Industry standards - OST OST is developed for standard technological processes, norms, requirements, rules, methods, etc. used and related to enterprises, institutions, offices of an industry and approved by the Ministry (department) of the industry (enters into force, changes or repeals). will be done). Compliance with the requirements of the OST is mandatory for all enterprises and departments of the industry, as well as other industry agencies and enterprises that use their products in this field.

3. Standards of the Union Republics - RST Republican standards are created for products manufactured in the territory of the Republic, except for products belonging to GOST and OST, approved (entered into force, amended or repealed) by the relevant departments of the Republic and subject to its requirements. is mandatory for offices and institutions.

4. Enterprise standard - STP STP is developed for the norms, requirements, rules, methods, etc. adopted for an enterprise, approved by the head of the enterprise (comes into force, amended or repealed, and compliance with its

requirements is mandatory for the enterprise). Normative and technical documents for medicines and herbal products are developed in accordance with the industry standard OST 42-1-71 "Procedures for development, coordination and approval of normative and technical documents for medicines and medicinal plants" approved by the Ministry of Health. Normative and technical documents must ensure continuous improvement of the quality of medicines and constantly improve their requirements on the basis of scientific and technical achievements.

Normative and technical documents for medicinal products and medicinal plant products are as follows: State standards - GOST, Pharmacopoeia article - FS, temporary pharmacopoeia article - VFS and industry standard - OST (scientific and technical terms, general technical documents, technological norms, rules of acceptance, designation, marking, storage, shipping rules, etc.).

GOST is developed and approved by Gosstandart for plant products that are produced in large quantities and used in all sectors of the economy. FS is a multi-series, medicinal and herbal product approved by the Ministry of Health for use in the medical field, as well as approved by the Head of the Scientific and Technical Department of the Ministry of Health.

VFS - The first industrially produced copies of new drugs recommended for use in medicine by the Pharmacological Committee of the Ministry of Health, and later intended for mass production, and new types of medicinal plants are approved. VFS is approved for a short period, but not more than 3 years. VFS and FS are equated to state standards (GOST). Therefore, all enterprises, institutions and agencies that produce, control and use medicinal products and herbal products must comply with the requirements of FS and VFS. The State Pharmacopoeia is an article on a long-running pharmacopoeia of medicinal plants and medicinal plant products that has been widely used in the treatment of diseases and has not lost its value. The State Pharmacopoeia also contains various articles (on physical, physicochemical, chemical and biological methods of analysis, reagents used in drug analysis, indicators, instruments, containers, etc.), which have a legal content. Therefore, the implementation of the State Pharmacopoeia in relation to medicinal products and medicinal plant products is mandatory for enterprises, institutions and agencies that produce, control, maintain and use them in the territory of the Republic. The State Pharmacopoeia and the Pharmacopoeia article are periodically reviewed and reaffirmed, and the old ones lose their validity.

All normative and technical documents on medicinal plant products (FS, VFS, GOST, etc.) have the same structure and information is given in the same

order. The title of the article gives the name of the medicinal plant product in Latin, Russian and the state language. In the introduction, the Latin names of the plant and its family, as well as what plant (wild or cultivated) the product is made from and when it was prepared (harvesting period or plant growth stage). Then the sections of the FS begin:

The "External signs" section gives the morphological features of the product as a whole, in the form of a powder, as well as the smell and taste of the product (for non-toxic products). The "Microscopy" section provides specific diagnostic features of the anatomical structure of the product and the microchemical reactions that take place during microscopic analysis.

In the section "Qualitative reactions" the product is specific to biological substances and important reactions in determining the authenticity of the product, chromatographic analysis and methods of their implementation are given.

The "Quantitative indicators" section lists the biologically active substances that must be present in the product and the permissible amounts (moisture, total ash, ash and mixtures insoluble in 10% hydrochloric acid) and other parts of the plant (defective products, organic and mineral compounds, etc.). The section "Quantitative determination" provides a detailed description of the methods for determining the main biologically active substance (or biological activity) of the product, or indicates in which part of the State Pharmacopoeia these methods are given.

"Placement" - in the packaging section, you can specify in which container (bag, box, box, bag, etc.) the product is placed.

The "Marking", "Shipping" and "Storage" sections list the requirements for marking dyes used during the shipment of medicinal plant products in vehicles and for storage of the product in warehouses and pharmacies (described above).

Determining and analyzing the authenticity of medicinal plant products. The analysis of medicinal plant products begins with determining their authenticity (corresponding to their names). It is considered that the raw material corresponds to its name, the amount of biologically active substances in it and the product meets the requirements of regulatory and technical documents. Therefore, the analysis of medicinal plant raw materials begins with the determination of their authenticity, and then the idea of their high quality.

Determining the authenticity of products is done in different ways depending on in which case they were sent for analysis. Medicinal plant products are delivered to warehouses and pharmacies without being crushed - whole, cut to a certain size and ground into a powder. So, in this case, they are also sent for

analysis. If the products are sent for analysis whole, uncut, their authenticity depends only on their appearance - morphologically, semi-microscopically, large-cut - mainly on the macroscopic and partially anatomical structure, ie microscopically, the medicinal plant products are finely chopped or powdered. - can be detected only by microscopic method if it is powdered. In product analysis, microchemical and chemical reactions to certain biologically active substances help to determine their authenticity. Microchemical analysis to determine the authenticity of medicinal plant products. Histochemical reactions provide additional information to determine the authenticity of a medicinal plant product. In addition, histochemical reactions can detect the accumulation of chemicals in cells and tissues. This is important in solving practical problems related to the use of plant products.

Because histochemical reactions help to detect even very small amounts of substances, care and cleanliness must be observed when carrying out this work. Because of the specificity of histochemical reactions, other substances that react to the test object must be pre-isolated. The section prepared for the histochemical reaction does not have to be very thin, but 2-3 cell thick. It should also be noted that very small amounts of the reactant must be exposed to very small amounts of the reactant. Since many of the reactions used in histochemical reactions are not nodular, they must be freshly prepared and stored separately. Histochemical reactions are carried out in wet and specially preserved plant sections. If, as a result of a reaction, it is necessary to determine the presence of a substance, but not its place of accumulation, then the reaction is carried out in a crushed dry plant (sawdust, powder) and the reaction is called a microchemical reaction. Depending on the nature of the reagent and the time of exposure, the reaction is carried out on an instrument glass, a watch glass or a beaker. As a result, it is seen under a microscope, first in a small lens and then in a large lens. Many histochemical reactions need to be carried out and monitored rapidly, otherwise the plant tissue may disintegrate under the influence of the reagent.

Reaction to cellulose. 1. Reaction with zinc-chlorine-iodine. Place the incision correctly in 1 drop of water on the beaker, filter the water with a filter paper, add 1 drop of chlorine-zinc-iodine reagent to the incision, cover with a cover glass and view under a microscope. The cell wall made of real cellulose is painted blue-purple. Reaction to wood fiber

. 1 Reaction with fluoroglucin and hydrochloric acid. The incision is placed in a 1% alcohol solution of fluoroglucin in a glass slide, then the reagent is soaked with a filter paper and 1 drop of concentrated hydrochloric acid is added to the

slice. Wooden cell walls are painted from pink to dark red, depending on the degree of wooding.

2. Reaction with saffron. The cut is placed in a 1% solution of saffron in 50% alcohol in a beaker or watch glass. After 30 minutes, it is first washed with 50% alcohol and then with acid-retaining alcohol, and the saffron is removed from the non-woody part of the tissue. The stained cut is then placed in glycerin on a glass slide and viewed under a microscope. The walls of the wooden cells are painted red.

Reaction to starch. The test piece or powder is placed in a Lugol's solution (potassium iodide solution of iodine) on a glass slide and the cover is flashed with a glass slide and viewed under a microscope. In this case, the starch granules are dyed blue or blue-purple. Heating the drug leads to discoloration.

Reaction to inulin. A slice of the test piece (wet state) is soaked in 70% alcohol for several days and examined under a microscope in alcohol or glycerin. Inulin spherical crystals, which are composed of small crystals, are visible. The presence of inulin, starch and sugar can also be transmitted by the Molish reaction. To do this, the cut is placed on a glass slide with a solution of naphthol (or thymol) in 10-20% alcohol, 1 drop of concentrated sulfuric acid is added, sealed with a cover glass and viewed under a microscope. In this case, carbohydrates (inulin, starch, sugar) turn red-purple or orange-red.

Reaction to mucous substances. a). The dream reaction involves placing the powder of the product under test in an aqueous solution of black dream (1:10) on a glass slide and covering it with a cover glass and viewing it under a microscope. Against a black background, mucus-containing cells appear as white spots.

b). Reaction with methylene blue: the cut is placed in a solution of methylene blue in alcohol (1: 5000) on a glass slide for a few minutes and then added to glycerin and examined under a microscope. In this case, the mucous substances dye the air.

v). Reaction with copper sulfate and alkali: the cut is placed on a glass slide in a concentrated solution of copper sulfate for 5-10 minutes, then washed with water and a 50% solution of potassium alkali is added to it. In this case, the mucous substances become airy or green.

Reaction to fats. Reaction with Sudan: The section is immersed in Sudan III solution for 1 day and examined under a microscope. The oil droplets turn an orange-red color. This reaction is not typical of roads, as it is caused by essential oils, resins and other plant substances. Therefore, the presence of fats is again determined by the saponification reaction.

Rosenthal soaping: the cut is placed in a 15% solution of potassium hydroxide on a glass slide and heated slightly. After a few minutes, the salts of the fatty acids (soap) appear as pine-shaped crystals. Reaction to essential oils. Essential oils are identified with Sudan III as oils. To distinguish essential oils from oils and resins, the test drug is placed in a solution of methylene blue in water for a few minutes (0.1 g of methylene blue is dissolved in 500 ml of water) and examined under water or under a microscope. In this case, the essential oils turn blue

is painted. Other methods are also used to determine the presence of essential oils. When the drug is heated with water, the essential oils evaporate, and when heated with dye reagents, the essential oils evaporate and do not react with the dye reagents.

Reaction to resins. Resins can also react with dyes such as oil, ether, Sudan III or other reagents. But these reactions are not characteristic. They can be identified by the following reaction.

Reaction with copper acetate. The test piece is placed in a concentrated solution of copper acetate for several days. A cut is then made, placed on a glass slice, covered with a cover glass and viewed under a microscope. In this case, the resins are painted green.

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